

STIFFNESS BASED FATIGUE DAMAGE CHARACTERISATION OF FIBROUS COMPOSITES

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We present a simple procedure for measuring the changes in stiffness properties of a unidirectional fibrous composite caused by fatigue damage. Unlike previous attempts at stiffness based fatigue damage characterization, where one or two elastic constants have been investigated, we consider changes in all four independent stiffness constants of an orthotropic elastic lamina. The results obtained for a unidirectional glass fibre reinforced polyester show that while small changes occur in the longitudinal elastic modulus and the Poisson's ratio of transverse to longitudinal strains, the shear modulus and the Poisson's ratio of longitudinal to transverse strains change significantly.

The extension of this procedure to the fatigue damage characterization of laminates is discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The complexity of the micromechanisms of fatigue damage in fibrous composites necessitates a damage characterization based on a macroscopically measurable set of parameters. The two procedures for characterization investigated hitherto have been based on the strength degradation and the stiffness changes. It is generally accepted now that the strength degradation does not always reflect the fatigue damage. The stiffness properties on the other hand have been found to change continuously with fatigue cycles and therefore could provide basis for a non-destructive procedure for fatigue damage characterization. It must, however, be realized that use of this procedure assumes that the integrity of the laminate is maintained and that it behaves as a linearly elastic material.

Previous investigations related to stiffness changes, e.g. [1-4], have been content with considering a single parameter (usually the longitudinal E-modulus) to indicate the occurrence of fatigue damage. A complete characterization of fatigue damage would require measuring changes in all stiffness components and relating these to the damage mechanisms. This has not been reported for any fibrous composite. The present investigation is intended as an attempt leading to the development of a procedure for a complete characterization of fibrous composite laminates.

The essential first step in the fatigue damage characterization of laminates is to measure changes in the stiffness properties of a lamina. Considering a lamina to be an orthotropic elastic material the stiffness properties are given by the longitudinal elastic modulus E_{11} , the transverse elastic modulus E_{22} , the two Poisson's ratios ν_{12} and ν_{21} and the in-plane shear modulus G_{12} . The relation $E_{11}\nu_{21} = E_{22}\nu_{12}$ reduces the number of independent elastic constants to four. The problem is now to devise an experimental procedure to record changes in all these four parameters with fatigue cycling. A continuous measurement of all four parameters without interrupting fatigue testing does not appear feasible. A procedure is therefore sought to intermittently measure the elastic constants. One approach would be to reshape the fatigue specimen, for instance by cutting out an off-axis specimen from it, at the end of a given number of fatigue cycles and measure the elastic constants on it. It would, however, be more desirable to measure all the elastic constants on the fatigue specimen and leave it undisturbed for further fatigue cycling. In a recent paper [5] a procedure to measure all four constants on a unidirectional composite, which involves tests in longitudinal, transverse, shear and flexure modes, has been proposed. Herein we present a specimen design which allows fatigue loading as well as measurement of all four elastic constants involving much less effort and time.

MATERIAL AND SPECIMEN

The material used was a unidirectional Glass Fibre Reinforced Polyester with 28% fibre volume fraction. The material was fabricated as flat plates of approximately 3 mm thickness by winding glass rovings on a rectangular frame. From the central parts of these plates the specimens were cut out and shaped.

The specimen is shown in Fig. 1. The procedure for preparing the specimen was as follows. From a rectangular plate of GFRP a piece slightly larger than the specimen was cut out by a saw. A templet of steel having dimensions 1 mm less than the specimen dimensions was glued to the GFRP piece by a tape having glue on both faces. The specimen was then shaped using a rotating cylindrical steel cutter to the dimensions of the templet plus a constant distance of 1 mm. The specimen edges thus prepared were fairly flat and parallel to the templet edges, which were machined accurately to be perpendicular to the templet faces. The specimen was detached from the templet at the end of the shaping process. Aluminium tabs of 1.5 mm thickness were then glued to the specimen ends using an epoxy adhesive film. Rectangular steel plates of 6 mm thickness were connected by bolts to the specimen ends through 4 holes of 8 mm dia. as shown in Fig. 1. Strain gauge rosettes of $3 \times 120^\circ$ type were applied at the centre of the specimen, one on each side, with one of the gauges aligned with the longitudinal axis of the specimen.

Fig. 1. The specimen.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The experimental procedure consisted of applying fatigue loads in the (longitudinal) fibre direction and stopping the test intermittently to measure the four elastic constants.

The fatigue loading was applied in a servo hydraulic testing machine at a frequency of 10 Hz. The loading was applied through pins in the 12 mm dia. holes along the longitudinal centre line in the steel plates attached to the specimen (Fig. 1). The pin holders were of the type used for fracture toughness testing of compact tension specimen. Only tension-tension cycles were applied.

The procedure for measuring the elastic constants was as follows. At the end of a chosen number of cycles the specimen was unloaded to zero load. The specimen was then reloaded slowly in tension by manually operating the set point of the load signal. The analog signals of the load and the three strain outputs were plotted and the digital signals of these parameters were recorded at suitable intervals. The strain gauges of the same orientation were coupled to compensate for any bending strains. The specimen was loaded to a value below the maximum cyclic load. Records of the load and the strains were also made during unloading of the specimen. At the end of these measurements the specimen was detached by taking out the two pins from the holes along the centre line. The specimen was then tilted and the two pins were

placed in the 12 mm dia. holes aligned with the axis 15° off the longitudinal centre line (see Fig. 1). The specimen was thus positioned to have the load axis go through its centre point and make an angle of 15° to its longitudinal axis. A tensile load was applied slowly and simultaneous records of load and strains were made at intervals. The maximum tensile load was kept below that necessary to cause shear failure parallel to fibres.

At the end of this test, which will be referred to as the 15° off-axis test, the pins were removed and the specimen tilted to place the pins in the 12 mm holes aligned with the -15° axis. A test in this position was carried out as for the 15° off-axis test.

Finally, to measure the Poisson's ratio ν_{21} , the specimen was taken out of the loading fixture and placed flat on a table. A vice was placed with its grip-plates parallel to the specimen edges and perpendicular to the plane of table. In this position the motion of the movable grip-plate was parallel to the transverse axis of the specimen. The grip-plates were brought in touch with the specimen edges and a slight clamping pressure was applied to take the initial strain readings. The specimen edges were then clamped further and the strains recorded. This was repeated a few times to check the repeatability of the strain measurements which was found to be satisfactory. Care was taken to grip the specimen edges away from the tab-ends in order to produce a uniform state of stress around the strain gauge location.

MEASUREMENT OF ELASTIC CONSTANTS

1. The longitudinal elastic modulus E_{11}

From the longitudinal tests the records of the load vs. the longitudinal strain was taken to calculate E_{11} . Alternatively, the modulus was calculated from the off-axis tests using the following relation.

$$E_{11} = \frac{P \cos 15^\circ}{A \epsilon_A} \tag{1}$$

where P is the load, A is the cross-sectional area and ϵ_A is the longitudinal strain (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Orientations of the strain gauges and the load axis in off-axis test with respect to the principal material axes.

The strain ϵ_A from the 15° off-axis test and from the -15° off-axis test should be the same for a given load. However, small differences were obtained due possibly to misalignments of gauges and/or the load axis. The average of the two moduli given by the two off-axis tests was found to differ by less than 2% from the modulus calculated from the longitudinal tests.

2. Poisson's ratio ν_{12}

This ratio was calculated from the strain outputs obtained in the longitudinal tests. The following relation was used to calculate this constant.

$$\nu_{12} = -\frac{\epsilon_{22}}{\epsilon_{11}} = \frac{1}{3} - \frac{4}{3} \frac{\epsilon_B}{\epsilon_A} = \frac{1}{3} - \frac{4}{3} \frac{\epsilon_C}{\epsilon_A} \quad (2)$$

The tensor transformation of strain components is used to derive this relation.

As indicates by Eq. (2), $\epsilon_B = \epsilon_C$. However, small differences in the two strains were observed due possibly to strain gauge misalignments. Average of the two strains was used in Eq. (2). The ratio was calculated for five load values and almost constant value was obtained.

3. Shear modulus G_{12}

The shear modulus was obtained by using the load and the strain outputs from the off-axis tests. Referring to Fig. 2 the shear stress is given by

$$\sigma_{12} = -\frac{P}{A} \sin 15^\circ \quad (3)$$

and the shear strain by

$$\gamma_{12} = 2\epsilon_{12} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} (\epsilon_B - \epsilon_C) \quad (4)$$

Thus the shear modulus is given by

$$G_{12} = \frac{\sigma_{12}}{\gamma_{12}} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \frac{P \sin 15^\circ}{A(\epsilon_C - \epsilon_B)} \quad (5)$$

Due to the symmetry of the specimen and the strain gauges the two strains ϵ_B and ϵ_C in the off-axis test should be numerically equal and differ only by sign. However, small differences were obtained. The initial shear modulus calculated by Eq. (5) was found to be in good agreement with the value obtained by an off-axis test on the same material with its fibres at 30° to the load axis.

4. Poisson's ratio ν_{21}

This ratio was calculated using the strain outputs from the transverse-clamping test using the relation:

$$\nu_{21} = -\frac{\epsilon_{11}}{\epsilon_{22}} = \frac{-3\epsilon_A}{4\epsilon_B - \epsilon_A} = \frac{-3\epsilon_A}{4\epsilon_C - \epsilon_A} \quad (6)$$

where tensor transformation of strain components is used (see Fig. 2).

As indicated by Eq. (6) the two strains ϵ_B and ϵ_C should be equal. Small differences were however observed and the average of the two strains was used in Eq. (6). The initial ratio thus calculated was found in good agreement with the value obtained by an off-axis test on the same material with its fibres at 30° to the load axis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the measured initial values of the four elastic constants and the calculated value of E_{22} .

Fig. 3. Variation of E_{11} .

Fig. 4. Variation of ν_{12}

Fig. 5. Variation of G_{12} .

Fig. 6. Variation of ν_{21} .

E_{11} GPa	E_{22} GPa	G_{12} GPa	ν_{12}	ν_{21}
36.110	14.598	3.157	0.235	0.095

Table 1. The initial elastic constants.

Figs. 3-6 show the variation of the four elastic constants normalized by their initial values with the number of cycles applied. All results in these figures are for the same specimen subjected to the cyclic stress of $52 \text{ MPa} \pm 38 \text{ MPa}$.

As seen in these figures the longitudinal elastic modulus E_{11} remains essentially constant. The Poisson's ratio ν_{12} shows a slight increase. The in-plane shear modulus G_{12} and the Poisson's ratio ν_{21} show significant changes.

It is believed that the degradation observed in both G_{12} and ν_{21} reflect matrix damage. No splitting parallel to the fibres was observed in the specimen under consideration which indicates absence of an extensive fibre breakage. Previous studies, e.g. [2], have indicated that fatigue damage is dominated by fibre breakage at high stresses while at low stresses matrix microcracking is the major damage mechanism. Due to the low stresses applied to the specimen in this investigation it may be expected that matrix cracking would dominate the fatigue damage. The variation in the shear modulus seems to indicate that the matrix damage might approach a saturation state. Since E_{11} and ν_{12} show small changes, the changes in E_{22} are essentially reflected by the changes in ν_{21} .

From the results described above it is apparent that changes in E_{11} alone do not reflect all damage events in fatigue of composites. Therefore, a damage characterization of composites cannot be based on the measured changes in E_{11} alone. A complete stiffness based characterization would require the totality of changes in all stiffness properties. Clearly, these changes must be related to the damage mechanisms, if possible, in a quantitative way. For instance, the matrix microcrack density may be related to the changes in E_{22} and G_{12} . Fibre debonding may affect E_{11} and interfacial damage might influence changes in ν_{12} .

EXTENSION TO LAMINATES

A lamina is the basic element of laminates. The laminated plate theory provides basis for relating the elastic properties of the individual laminae to the elastic properties of the laminate. It is to be expected, therefore, that changes induced by fatigue in the elastic properties of individual laminae would result in changes of the elastic properties of the laminate. A stiffness based fatigue damage characterization of laminates would therefore require establishing changes in the stiffness properties of the individual laminae induced by fatigue. The individual laminae however do not behave freely but are constrained by the neighbouring laminae. This constraint effect on fatigue induced stiffness property changes should therefore be investigated next.

The procedure described above for unidirectional composites can be extended to other configurations of laminates. One useful configuration to study the constraint effects would be the cross-ply laminates. This configuration is specially suited to study the matrix damage changes as the 90° plies provide the most direct suppression of matrix cracking.

CONCLUSION

A procedure to investigate the stiffness property changes induced by fatigue of unidirectional composites has been proposed. The results obtained for a unidirectional glass fibre reinforced polyester clearly demonstrates the necessity for considering all four stiffness properties for a complete characterization of the fatigue induced damage.

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